

MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES, ENVIRONMENT & CLIMATE CHANGE

DIRECTORATE OF ENVIRONMENT & CLIMATE CHANGE KANO STATE

BLOCK 5, AUDU BAKO SECRETARIAT, KANO STATE.

22nd June, 2026

The Director Climate Change,
Department of Climate Change,
Federal Ministry of Environment,
Abuja, Nigeria.

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to formally confirm that **Umar Saleh Anka**, the **Director of Climate Change/Climate Change Subnational Desk Officer**, has been duly authorized and approved to respond to the survey for the:

Third Edition of the Subnational Climate Governance Performance Ranking (SCGRPR3.0) 2026

He is empowered to represent Kano State in completing the survey and providing relevant data and information as required.

We understand and acknowledge that the information he provides will be used solely for the ranking purposes as outlined in the survey, and that all submissions will be treated with the utmost confidentiality.

Please extend to him the necessary cooperation as he undertakes this responsibility on behalf of the State Government.

Sincerely,

Mustapha Muhammad Nuraddeen
Permanent Secretary
For: Honourable Commissioner